

Usage scenarios of mathematical STACK problems at the Magdeburg-Stendal University of Applied Sciences

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Abstract: Mathematical STACK problems with automated feedback offer students digital opportunities to consolidate their mathematical skills anywhere and anytime. During the winter term 2022/23, our team has started systematically integrating weekly digital problems and regular e-assessments into the curricular mathematics courses for civil engineers at the Magdeburg-Stendal University of Applied Sciences. Monitoring and statistical analysis of students' usage behaviour and learning success have been complemented by two structured surveys during the teaching period. The obtained results provide the basis for further improvements of the general course design and specific integration scenario of STACK problems into the curricular mathematics courses in different engineering programs.

Keywords: Mathematics for Civil Engineers, STACK problems with automated feedback, e-assessments.

1 Introduction

With the recent Covid-19 pandemic, the demand for carefully developed digital materials supporting student's self-study processes in STEM has abruptly increased. One of the main outcomes of the corresponding achievements was a renewed support of the long-standing hypothesis that digital formats in general, and digital mathematics problems and their automatic assessment, provide powerful tools to boost the learning success even in regular teaching scenarios. Based on previous experiences using mathematics problems

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developed using the commercial software WIRIS/CalcMe and embedded as tests in the learning management system Moodle, in 2021 Magdeburg-Stendal University of Applied Sciences has started a transition process involving the implementation of STACK into a digital mathematics learning support centre as well as courses of engineering mathematics in different study programs. Regarding the latter aspect, the Civil Engineering bachelor program with its courses Mathematics 1-3 has been serving as a first testbed for implementing weekly selections of digital STACK problems along with regular (3 to 4-weekly) voluntary e-assessments.

2 German database of mathematical STACK problems

The used material is largely based on two existing, not fully independent collections of German-language mathematical STACK problems, DOMAIN (<https://db.ak-mathe-digital.de>, Ruhr University Bochum) and DIGITALER AUFGABENPOOL MATHEMATIK (<https://aufgabenpool.th-koeln.de>, Cologne University of Applied Sciences). Following the curricula of our Mathematics for Civil Engineering courses, the available problems have been carefully categorized into topical blocks matching those of the lecture series, assessed for duplicates, checks for proper terminology and symbolization, understandable language, and technical correctness. In parallel to working with the existing problems, some additional problems for previously underrepresented topics have been developed whenever necessary.

3 Exploitation of mathematical STACK problems

The accordingly quality-controlled STACK problems have been exploited in two separate ways. On the one hand, the problems have been grouped into topical categories and made available as digital tests in a specific Moodle course are associated with a digital mathematics learning support centre, which additionally features selected self-study materials (like publicly available explanatory videos) and contacts to student tutors offering regular on-site help classes on a voluntary basis. On the other hand, a selection of typically 3-4 problems per week are being implemented as self-assessments into the Moodle course area of the respective lecture series Mathematics 1, 2 and 3 for Civil Engineers. These are complemented by voluntary on-site STACK-based e-assessments during the lectures held every 3-4 weeks within the teaching period, from which the students can obtain bonus points for the final written exam of the course. Utilization of the different STACK problems and corresponding success rates are continuously monitored.

During the winter term 2022/23, the course Mathematics 1 (covering basic concepts, linear algebra, and analytical geometry with two academic hours of lectures and practical sessions each per week) was the first course completely supported by the weekly selected training problems and regular e-assessments. Figure 1 shows the timeline of the course including the intermediate e-assessments.

Fig. 1: Timeline of weekly self-assessments, bonus tests and final exam (cw = calendar week).

Figure 2 summarizes the results of the final exam of the course (regular maximum of 64 points plus extra points from a supplementary problem and the intermediate e-assessments) versus the total views of all provided digital STACK problems by each student. Despite a generally large scatter, our data suggest a weak but generally positive statistical association (linear $r^2=.18$). This supports previous findings of positive statistical associations between usage of digital tests and learning materials and examination success during the Mathematics 2 courses in the summer term 2022, where digital problems based on WIRIS/CalcMe have been utilized [Do23]. In summary, the implementation of STACK problems via voluntary weekly exercises and regular e-assessments demonstrates considerable potentials for supporting the learning success of students as evidenced by the examination results. Whether the found correlation is due to a direct causal link or common explanatory variables is currently subject of further in-depth studies.

Fig. 2: Total number of views of STACK problems versus total score in exam for each student.

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